

DIMENSIONAL STABILITY OF COMPOSITES IN SPACE: CTE VARIATIONS AND THEIR PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

In this study the applicability of strain gages to measure near-zero CTEs of composites for space structures is investigated. Adequate precautions are employed to minimize errors due to apparent strains which arise when the gage element is heated by the excitation current as well as from differential resistances of gages, leads and lead wires. The accuracy and reproducibility of the technique is verified from tests on standard alloys, while its ability to measure very low CTEs (of the order of $1 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) is validated by the excellent agreement between measured and predicted lamina and laminate CTEs. It is also sensitive to changes in CTE induced by microcracking brought about by thermal cycling.

INTRODUCTION

Composites are steadily replacing metals in weight-critical spacecraft structures primarily because of their high specific strengths and moduli. Many space structures require not only high stiffness but precision alignment and dimensional stability as well, which makes the low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of carbon fiber composites attractive. The major concerns that govern the use of polymer-based composites in space are their long-term behavior and reliability. Extreme hot and cold thermal cycling conditions exist in orbit, and severe thermal gradients within the same part (as a result of shadowing, edge heating or solar exposure of the front or back surface only) are not uncommon. These thermal gradients cause internal stresses which can result in mechanical deformations. The lower the CTE of the composite, the less the distortion, making the use of a material with a tailorable near-zero CTE a major advantage. The thermal cycling is particularly detrimental to resin-matrix composites because it can result in microcracking due to the processing-induced residual stresses within the composite. This microcracking can cause a significant reduction in the composite CTE [1] and degrade matrix-dominated properties such as shear and compression strengths. The susceptibility of a composite to microcracking can be reduced with the use of higher-strain matrix resins and lower cure temperatures, although these conditions may adversely influence the material's response to radiation and moisture exposure.

Since CTE is a key property in the selection of materials and design of structures for the space environment it must be determined with both accuracy and reliability. A number of techniques have been employed to measure CTE including dilatometry, thermomechanical analysis (TMA), laser interferometry [2] and strain gages [3]. Each technique has its disadvantages: dilatometry requires a large specimen size for increased accuracy; TMA uses a small specimen size which may not be representative of the entire composite; and laser interferometry requires an expensive experimental setup while offering limited resolution and accuracy. A strain gage has the disadvantage of covering a relatively small area of the composite; however, thermal strains from a number of gages can be monitored simultaneously in a single run to provide an average CTE of the composite. The technique is inexpensive and readily accessible in most test laboratories. In

addition it is particularly conducive to in situ measurements on selected sites of the composite, for example, for correlation with localized environmental or mechanical damage. However, appropriate care must be taken to ensure accuracy by eliminating artifacts associated with the strain measurement.

Composite laminates can be tailored to a near-zero CTE which is essential to maintaining the dimensional stability of composite structures in the space environment. However, laminate CTE can change in service due to physical damage or property changes associated with exposure to temperature fluctuations, outgassing, atomic oxygen, radiation, etc. In this study the CTE of a candidate material for space structures - P-100X HTS/954-2A, a high-modulus graphite fiber-reinforced cyanate ester - was investigated using strain gages, with the technique refined to improve accuracy and reproducibility of the thermal strains.

CTE MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Composite CTEs were measured using strain gage techniques in conjunction with a computer-controlled temperature chamber and data acquisition system. Due to the extremely small longitudinal CTE of this material (of the order of $1 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) in both unidirectional composites and in multidirectional laminates containing 0° plies, ultra-low expansion titanium silicate (with a maximum thermal strain of 10 ppm over the temperature range of interest) was used as the reference material. WK-series 350Ω strain gages (6.35-mm gage length) from Micro-Measurements, Inc. were employed for this study. Heat generation in the strain gage from the excitation current, which gives rise to an apparent strain, was minimized by reducing the input voltage to the strain gage circuit to one volt. Two strain gages, one on the reference specimen and one on the test specimen, were taken from the same manufacturing lot to assure a close match of their apparent strain outputs. The strain gages were mounted with a high-temperature adhesive, cured as recommended by the manufacturer, and connected as adjacent arms of the bridge circuit. The output (apparent strain) of this half-bridge configuration is equal to the difference in the individual strains. This difference becomes zero when the two gages are electrically identical. Extremely stable precision resistors were used to complete the strain gage bridge. All lead wires were of equal length and maintained physically together throughout their length to minimize differential resistance changes. The reference and test specimens were placed near each other in a forced-air convection oven to minimize temperature differences. The temperatures of the specimen and oven were measured with separate thermocouples to check for thermal lag between them. Up to four strain gages were mounted on a composite specimen which with complementary gages on the reference material formed four strain gage bridges.

The measurement system can accommodate five channels; one was used for temperature and the remaining four for collecting thermal strains. A software program controlled the chamber temperature, allowing prescribed ramps to a series of temperatures, holds for a fixed period of time to allow the specimen temperature to equilibrate, and continuous acquisition of temperature and strain data. Data were collected during both heating and cooling cycles. A specimen was cycled between -101°C and 121°C at a heating rate of $3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and held for 15 minutes at each increment of 22°C of temperature. Thermal strains recorded at the end of each holding period were utilized for determination of CTE. The resolution of strain and temperature measurement with this experimental setup is 1×10^{-6} and 0.56°C , respectively. The correction for transverse sensitivity of the strain gage was made from the transverse sensitivity supplied by the manufacturer. Since the longitudinal thermal strain is two orders of magnitude smaller than the transverse thermal strain of a unidirectional composite, the transverse sensitivity correction is significant. Furthermore, the transverse sensitivity of the WK series gage employed is approximately 4%, which is an order of magnitude greater than other types of gages. The gage factor correction was also performed according to the the calibration curve supplied with the strain gages.

MEASUREMENT ACCURACY AND RELIABILITY

The accuracy and reliability of this CTE measurement method was verified with two materials of known CTE, aluminum Al-2024-T4 and titanium Ti-6Al-4V alloys. Figures 1 and 2 show the thermal strains obtained for the aluminum alloy (four strain gages) and for the titanium alloy (two strain gages), respectively. The symbols represent the experimental data. Linear fits to the data, represented by the solid lines, show very little deviation of the thermal strains from linear behavior. The average CTE, from the slopes of these lines, is $22.81 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $8.78 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the aluminum and titanium alloys, respectively. These values compare very well with the corresponding published handbook values of $23.22 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $8.82 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The excellent reproducibility of the measurement technique was demonstrated by a variation of less than one percent in the CTE between consecutive measurements with all six strain gages. Between runs the strain gage lead wires were detached and re-soldered to simulate actual measurements. Although strain gages on the test specimen and reference specimen are from the same manufacturing lot, this does not guarantee that their electrical properties will be identical. To examine this effect four strain gages were mounted on the reference material, titanium silicate. Two gages were used as reference gages, while the other two were used as test gages with one reference gage and one test gage forming a half-bridge. If the titanium silicate is assumed to be homogeneous in thermal expansion, any output from this arrangement is considered apparent strain due to difference in electrical properties between the reference gage and test gage. Figure 3 shows the result of six measurements with this setup, with various combinations of the four strain gages as test and reference gages. The measured CTE from this exercise ranged from near zero to $1.8 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

CTE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINA

Lamina longitudinal and transverse CTEs are fundamental thermal properties of a composite material and are used to calculate the thermal properties of various laminate orientations. To measure these CTEs a rectangular coupon 25 mm wide and 100 mm long was sectioned from an $[0]_{16}$ composite panel. Two longitudinal and two transverse strain gages were mounted with a high temperature adhesive which was cured for four hours at 163°C . Thermal strains from all four gages were measured simultaneously in the temperature range of -101°C to 121°C . The temperature was first raised to 121°C , held at this temperature for 15 minutes to allow the specimen to equilibrate, and strains recorded as the specimen was cooled to -101°C . Because of the considerable scatter of the extremely small longitudinal CTE, a total of five specimens were tested in this manner for this property. Figures 4 and 5 show some typical strain data recorded. The longitudinal thermal strain is corrected for the transverse sensitivity of the strain gages. The longitudinal CTE above 25°C appears to be slightly different from the value below 25°C , with an average value of $-1.02 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The transverse thermal strains show linear behavior (with a CTE of $36.7 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) and are an order of magnitude greater than the longitudinal strains.

CTE OF OFF-AXIS AND MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

The CTEs of unidirectional composites at angles of 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 80, and 85 degrees to the fiber direction were calculated using laminated plate theory and the results compared with experimental data. Two strain gages were mounted on each specimen at right angles to each other to simultaneously obtain thermal strains for two off-axis angles. For small off-axis angles the correction for transverse sensitivity becomes significant, and it was therefore employed for all thermal strains. Figure 6 shows typical thermal strains for a 15° off-axis specimen in the axial (15°) and transverse (75°) directions. The 75° off-axis strain varies linearly with temperature in the range studied, -101°C to 121°C , while the 15° off-axis strain shows a deviation from linearity around room temperature, as was observed for the 0° longitudinal thermal strain (Fig. 4). Figure 7 shows a comparison of the experimentally-determined CTEs with analytical predictions calculated from classical laminated plate theory. In most cases experiment and prediction agree well. Slight discrepancies in some cases are possibly due to a limitation of the current technique with respect to apparent strains from the strain gages and the difficulty in accurately aligning strain gages along small off-axis angles.

CTEs of $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates were also determined experimentally. Specimens, 5 cm x 5 cm in size, were sectioned and their edges polished. Microscopic examination of these specimen edges revealed no damage in the quasi-isotropic specimen and very few transverse cracks in the center $[90]_2$ layer of the cross-ply laminate (less than 1 cm^{-1}). Four strain gages, two longitudinal and two transverse, were mounted on each specimen away from any cracks. The thermal strains of both laminate orientations, shown in Figures 8 and 9, appear to be fairly linear in the temperature range studied. Theoretically, longitudinal and transverse strains in both cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates are identical, and the predicted CTE is $-0.35 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$. The experimental values, on the other hand, are $-0.59 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ for the cross-ply laminate and $-0.98 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ for the quasi-isotropic laminate, with coefficients of variation of 29% and 22%, respectively. The source of this scatter as well as the discrepancy between experiment and prediction is probably material variations within the laminates themselves, which arise from nonuniformity of ply thickness of the thin plies (0.064 mm) employed in the lay-up, as well as local variations in fiber alignment and fiber volume.

INFLUENCE OF MICROCRACKING ON LAMINATE CTE

Cross-ply $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminates were used to investigate the change in laminate CTE, due to microcracking brought about by thermal cycling, and simultaneously evaluate the sensitivity of this CTE measurement technique. The 5-cm x 5-cm squares tested above were initially cycled between -157°C and 121°C in the test chamber of a Rheometrics dynamic mechanical analyzer. Between cycles two polished edges were examined in a microscope to determine microcrack density in the center $[90]_2$ layer in the vicinity of the strain gages. A sketch of the specimen is shown in Figure 10. CTE was also measured periodically. After five cycles further microcracking was induced by immersing the specimen in liquid nitrogen and then allowing it to warm back to ambient temperature (cycling between -190°C and 23°C). Once again transverse cracks through the thickness of the center $[90]_2$ layer were taken as measures of damage induced by the thermal cycling. However, examination of the polished edges revealed additional damage via in-plane cracks in the $[90]_2$ layer. The cracks through the thickness reached saturation at 58 cm^{-1} after only 30 cycles, although cracks in other layers, both in-plane and through the thickness, continued to grow. The nature of the damage is evident from typical photomicrographs of the central $[90]_2$ layer shown in Figure 11. Also evident in this figure is the variation in the $[90]_2$ layer thickness at two different locations within 6 mm of each other. The longitudinal thermal strains of the specimen before and after thermal cycling are shown in Figure 12. The CTE of this specimen changed from $-0.59 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ in the undamaged state to $-0.88 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ after microcrack density in the central $[90]_2$ layer reached saturation.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Strain gages provide an inexpensive yet accurate means of measuring the CTE of composite laminates provided care is taken to avoid extraneous sources of error. These include apparent strains due to heating of the gage element and differential resistances of the gages, leads and lead wires. WK-series gages from Micro-Measurements, Inc. were employed to determine lamina and laminate CTEs of P-100X HTS/954-2A, a composite material intended for application in space structures. Measurements on standard alloys verified the accuracy and reproducibility of this technique, while comparison of experimental and predicted CTEs for off-axis laminates validated its applicability for the measurement of very low CTEs (of the order of $1 \times 10^{-7}/^\circ\text{C}$). Lamina thermal strains of this composite material varied linearly with temperature over the range studied. The CTE of multidirectional laminates varied with location due to the nonuniformity in ply thickness and fiber volume. Microcracking, induced by thermal cycling, is reflected in a change in laminate CTE. However, due to the very high stiffness in the fiber direction, the absolute change in CTE is minimal. The use of strain gages provides the flexibility to correlate localized damage with changes in composite CTE.

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FIGURE 1. Thermal strains of Al-2024-T4; four measurements

FIGURE 2. Thermal strains of Ti-6Al-4V; two measurements

FIGURE 3. Apparent thermal strains from six combinations of two (reference and test) gages out of four strain gages on titanium silicate

FIGURE 4. Longitudinal thermal strain for a $[0]_{16T}$ laminate

FIGURE 5. Transverse thermal strain from a $[0]_{16T}$ laminate

FIGURE 6. Axial and transverse thermal strains for a 15° off-axis laminate

FIGURE 7. Predicted (solid line) and experimental (data points) composite CTEs as functions of off-axis angle.

FIGURE 8. Two longitudinal and two transverse thermal strains of a $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate.

FIGURE 9. Two longitudinal and two transverse thermal strains of a $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate.

FIGURE 10. Sketch of CTE test specimen showing strain gages and locations (x) of crack density measurements ($x=6.35$ mm)

FIGURE 12. Effect of microcracking (due to thermal cycling) on the thermal strains of a $[0/90]_4S$ laminate.

FIGURE 11. Micrographs showing microcracks in the central $[90]_2$ layer of a $[0/90]_4S$ laminate due to thermal cycling.